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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Self-Double Emulsifying Drug Delivery System Of Simvastatin

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ABSTRACT

The Self-Double Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SDEDDS) was a type of system where particles of one substance were dispersed within another. Simvastatin, a drug that lowered cholesterol, had a short half-life and only 5% bioavailability due to first-pass metabolism, making it a good candidate for SDEDDS. This study focused on improving Simvastatin's solubility and dissolution rate and various formulations of Simvastatin were prepared using SDEDDS, and all demonstrated quick emulsification times, high cloud points, and acceptable viscosity levels. The efficiency with which the drug was entrapped within the emulsions ranged from 82.12% to 97.75%, indicating a high level of effectiveness. A numerical optimization tool was employed to identify six optimal solutions, with the best combination consisting of 11 ml of olive oil, 52 ml of Span 80, and 10 ml of Tween 60, achieving a desirability score of 1.0. The optimized formulation exhibited an average particle size of 782.7 nm and a zeta potential of -46.4 mV, both of which are favorable for drug stability and absorption. Overall, this study demonstrated that SDEDDS could significantly improve the solubility, dissolution rate, and bioavailability of Simvastatin, potentially leading to enhanced therapeutic effects.

INTRODUCTION

Taking medicine by mouth is the most common and preferred method. However, this approach can be challenging due to the digestive system, which can impact how much of the drug is absorbed and how effectively it works. One significant issue

with oral medications is their poor dissolution rate. To address this, various techniques are used, such as employing drug carriers, forming drug salts, adding different surfactants, modifying the drug's structure, and using nanoparticles or liposomes [1]. Self-double emulsifying drug delivery systems

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(SDEDDS) are designed to enhance the solubility and dissolution rate of drugs that do not dissolve well in water. These systems exploit principles of self-emulsification to create a stable double emulsion, which help hydrophobic drugs disperse better, improving their absorption and bioavailability while also enabling tailored release profiles and reduced side effects. There are two types of double emulsions: water-in-oil-in-water (w/o/w) and oil-in-water-in-oil (o/w/o) [2]. Simvastatin is a statin drug that lowers LDL cholesterol levels by blocking the enzyme HMG CoA reductase. It belongs to BCS class II, meaning it has low solubility but high permeability. The effectiveness of oral simvastatin depends on how well it dissolves from its dosage form. This study focused on improving the poor water solubility of simvastatin [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preformulation Study

Preformulation studies focus on the physicochemical properties of a drug that could impact its performance and dosage form development. This is the first step in creating a stable, safe, and effective dosage form, aiming to establish the drug's kinetic rate profile and compatibility with other ingredients [4].

Analytical Methods

Calibration Curve of Simvastatin in pH 7 Phosphate Buffer

Calibration curve of Simvastatin is made by dissolving 100 mg of Simvastatin in methanol, then diluting it to 100 ml with phosphate buffer to achieve a concentration of 1000 ppm (Stock Solution A). From this solution, 10 ml is taken and further diluted with phosphate buffer to obtain Stock Solution B at 100 ppm. From this, pipette out aliquots of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, and 2 ml and diluted with phosphate buffer to get concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 ppm. Absorbance is measured at 238 nm,

and a graph is plotted with concentration on the x-axis and absorbance on the y-axis [5].

Solubility Study

The solubility of Simvastatin in various oils, lipophilic surfactants, and hydrophilic surfactants is determined using the flask shake method. Excess drug is added to 250 ml conical flasks containing 100 ml of different oils and surfactants, and the flasks are shaken using a rotary shaker. The samples are filtered through Whatman filter paper, and absorbance is measured at 238 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. Solubility is calculated using the formula [6]:

Solubility = (Absorbance of sample / Absorbance of standard solution) × Concentration of standard solution × Dilution factor.

Construction of Pseudo-Ternary Phase Diagrams

Ternary phase diagrams are used to determine the concentration range of components. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams are constructed using the water titration method. Plots are created with oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant in different ratios (1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, 4:1). The mixtures are diluted by adding water drop by drop under magnetic stirring. Data is used to construct ternary plots with a ternary plot maker [7].

Drug-Excipient Compatibility

FTIR spectroscopy is used to study drug-excipient compatibility. FTIR spectra of the pure drug, olive oil, Span 80, Tween 60, and their physical mixtures are recorded. The peaks of the pure drug, oil, surfactant, co-surfactant, and physical mixtures are compared to check for incompatibility [8].

Formulation of Self-Double-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System of Simvastatin

W/O/W double emulsion is prepared using a modified two-step emulsification method. The self-double-emulsifying drug delivery system (SDEDDS) changes the second emulsification step to self-emulsify into a w/o/w double emulsion due

to gastrointestinal peristaltic movements in vivo, instead of artificial emulsification in vitro. The drug is dissolved in water, then oil and lipophilic

surfactant are added to form the primary w/o emulsion. Hydrophilic surfactant is then added to form the w/o/w double emulsion [9].

Table no.1: Formulation of SDEDDS of simvastatin

Formulations	Simvastatin(mg)	Olive oil(ml)	Water (ml)	Span 80 (ml)	Tween 60 (ml)	S/Co-S ratio
F1	20	25.86	15	19.02	38.82	1:2
F2	20	21.59	15	43.44	13.06	4:1
F3	20	18.70	15	24.72	24.72	1:1
F4	20	17.10	15	18.39	36.79	1:2
F5	20	16.84	15	10.80	43.22	1:4
F6	20	15.95	15	14.24	42.72	1:3
F7	20	15.25	15	50.24	12.56	4:1
F8	20	12.91	15	17.40	34.81	1:2
F9	20	11.10	15	52.73	10.86	4:1

Characterization of SDEDDS of Simvastatin

Drug Content

Formulations F1-F9 of self-double emulsifying drug delivery systems, each containing an equivalent to one dose, were added to a 10 ml volumetric flask containing water and mixed. The solution was further diluted and analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer at 238 nm [10].

Determination of Self-Emulsification Time and Cloud Point

A USP type II apparatus was used to determine the self-emulsification time of the developed formulations. 500 ml of water was placed in a dissolution flask and equilibrated at 37°C. One ml of the double emulsion was added to the flask and stirred at 50 rpm. The time required to form a homogenous dispersion was recorded as the self-emulsification time [11]. The emulsion becomes cloudy when the temperature increases. The temperature at which cloudiness is observed is noted and considered the cloud point. One ml of each formulation was diluted with water and heated in a water bath. The temperature was gradually increased, and the point at which cloudiness was observed was recorded [12].

Rheological Properties Determination

Viscosity studies are important for w/o/w double emulsion to ensure physical stability during

storage. The viscosity of the double emulsion was evaluated using a Brookfield viscometer with spindle 4 at 50 rpm [13].

Entrapment Efficiency

Percentage entrapment efficiency was determined by taking 1 ml of the double emulsion, diluting it with phosphate buffer (pH 7), and filtering the solution through Whatman filter paper. Drug content was analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer at 238 nm. The entrapment efficiency was calculated using the following equation [14]:

$$\%EE = \frac{\text{Drug content obtained (mg)}}{\text{Total amount of drug added (mg)}} \times 100$$

In-vitro Release Study

Dissolution studies were performed using a USP dissolution apparatus type II. The release studies were conducted at a paddle speed of 50 rpm in 900 ml of pH 7 phosphate buffer at 37±0.2°C. Two ml of the solution was withdrawn from the medium at intervals of 0, 5, 15, 30, 45, and 60 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 238 nm, and the percentage drug release was calculated [15].

Determination of Particle size

The particle size of developed formulation was determined by using Zeta Sizer [16].

Optimization of self-double emulsifying drug delivery system by response surface methodology (RSM)

The optimization of self-double emulsifying drug delivery system was done by using the design expert software (Design expert software stat ease version 13). The % of drug released in 60 minutes and % drug content were taken as the response variables [17].

Statistical analysis

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied for comparison of results. To demonstrate

graphically the influence of each factor on response and to indicate the optimum level of factors, the contour and response surface plots were generated using Design expert software (Stat-ease, 13). All the data measured and reported were averages of a minimum of triplicate measurement and the values are expressed as $\pm$ standard deviation [18].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Analytical method

Fig no. 1: Standard curve of Simvastatin in phosphate buffer pH 7 at 238nm

The drug was scanned in UV region (200-400) nm by using phosphate buffer pH 7 to find out wavelength of maximum absorption (λ max). The λ max was found to be 238nm. So the standard calibration curve of Simvastatin was developed at this wavelength. Standard calibration curve of Simvastatin was determined by using phosphate buffer pH 7 by plotting absorbance against concentration at 238nm

Physico-chemical properties of drug-
Organoleptic properties of simvastatin was studied

and concluded that simvastatin is a White to off-white crystalline powder, odourless & bitter and acrid in taste. The melting point was determined by capillary tube method and it was found to be $136 \pm 1.05^\circ\text{C}$.

Solubility profile

Solubility studies were carried out in different oils, lipophilic surfactants and hydrophilic surfactants and the result are showed in table 2, 3& 4

Table no. 2: Solubility profile of drug in different oils

Oils	Solubility
Coconut oil	Slightly soluble
Castor oil	Insoluble
Oleic acid	Insoluble
Olive oil	Soluble

Table no.3: Solubility profile of drug in different lipophilic surfactants

Surfactants	Solubility
Span 20	Slightly soluble
Span 40	Insoluble
Span 60	Slightly soluble
Span 80	Soluble

Table no. 4: Solubility profile of drug in different hydrophilic surfactants

Surfactants	Solubility
Tween 20	Insoluble
Tween 40	Slightly soluble
Tween 60	Soluble
Tween 80	Insoluble

Plot of pseudo ternary phase diagrams

Phase diagrams of the system containing olive oil as the oil phase, span 80 as the surfactant, and tween 60 as the co-surfactant were constructed at S:Cos ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 4:1 to determine the existence of microemulsion regions, as shown in Figures 1-5, respectively. The phase study revealed that the microemulsion region obtained at S/CoS ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4

was smaller compared to the S/CoS ratio of 4:1. As the concentration of the co-surfactant increases, the microemulsion region decreases, and as the concentration of the surfactant increases, the microemulsion region increases. This indicates that the concentration of the surfactant has a significant effect on the microemulsion region.

Fig no.2: Ternary plot of span 80: tween 60 = 1:1

Fig no. 3: Ternary plot of span 80: tween 60 = 1:2

Fig no.4: Ternary plot of Span 80: tween 60 = 1:3

Fig no 5: Ternary plot of span 80: tween 60 = 1:4

Fig no.6: Ternary plot of Span 80: tween 60 = 4:1

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies

Drug identification was done using FT-IR studies. The peaks of simvastatin were obtained at 3544 cm^{-1} (OH-aromatic stretching), 2927 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), and 1697 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching),

among others. There was no appearance of new peaks and no absence of any interfering peaks in the FT-IR spectra of the pure drug compared to the physical mixtures of the drug and polymers, indicating no drug-excipient incompatibility.

Fig no. 7: FT-IR Spectrum of Simvastatin

Fig no.7b: FT-IR Spectrum of Olive oil

Fig no.7a: FT-IR Spectrum of Span 80

Fig no.7c: FT-IR Spectrum Tween 60

Fig no. 7d: FT-IR Spectrum of Mixture

Drug content

The drug content of the 9 formulations was found to be between 90.5% and 99.1%. The percentage

of drug content for all SDEDDS formulations was within the acceptable limit of the drug content test.

Fig no.8: Drug content of formulation F1-F9

Determination of Self emulsification time and Cloud point

The self-emulsification time of all formulations (F1-F9) was less than 200 seconds, indicating that they can form emulsions rapidly upon exposure to GI fluid. A speed of 50 rpm was used, providing the lowest level of agitation, indicating that normal

GIT motility is sufficient for self-emulsification. Emulsions are unstable at higher temperatures, and the two phases tend to separate upon heating. The cloud point was above 50°C for all developed formulations, indicating their stability during processing and storage.

Table no.5: Self emulsification time and Cloud point of formulation F1-F9

Formulations	Self-emulsification time (seconds)	Cloud point °C
F1	179 ± 0.93	56 ± 1.64
F2	198 ± 1.28	57 ± 0.59
F3	156 ± 1.96	59 ± 1.08
F4	194 ± 1.27	57 ± 1.63
F5	168 ± 1.39	59 ± 2.01

F6	172 ± 1.02	56 ± 1.32
F7	163 ± 1.58	60 ± 2.52

Rheological properties determination

The formulation with the highest drug content F9 exhibited significantly higher viscosity ie 1531 cps

compared to other formulations, which is a positive indicator of stability and formulation performance.

Fig no.9: Viscosity of formulation F1-F9

Entrapment efficiency

The percentage entrapment efficiency of 9 formulations was found to be 82.12%- 97.75%

Fig no.10: % entrapment efficiency of

In-vitro release study

The in-vitro drug release of all the 9 formulations were carried out by using USP type II apparatus with phosphate buffer pH 7 as dissolution medium.

98.83%±0.37 of drug was released from F9 formulation within 60 minutes compared to other formulation

Fig no. 11: Cumulative percentage drug release
Particle size determination

	Z-Average (d,µm):	PDI:	Intercept:	Peak 1:	Peak 2:	Peak 3:	Diam. (nm)	% Intensity	Width (nm)
	782.7	0.910	0.835	686.7	129.9	5560	686.7	68.5	167.1
							129.9	28.3	26.08
							5560	3.2	0.000

Fig no.12: Particle size distribution curve

The particle size of developed formulation was analyzed by using Malvern Zeta Sizer instrument. The average particle size was found to be 782.7 nm, with polydispersity index 0.910 and the Zeta potential was found to be -46.4mV.

Optimization by Design Expert Software

Based on the fit summary, the quadratic model (Table No: 6) was selected as the best fit for %

release and % drug content (Table No: 8). The results of ANOVA (Table No: 7 and Table No: 9) indicated that the selected models were significant, and all response variables indicated the reliability of the models.

Response 1: In-vitro drug release

Table no.6: Fit summary

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of value	Adjusted R ²
Liner	0.222		0.4500
2FI	0.3670		0.4797

Quadratic	0.0029		0.9385
Cubic	0.4113		0.9756

Fig no.13: 3-D response surface plot for effect of concentration of olive oil, span80 and tween 60 on in-vitro drug release

Response 2: Drug content

Factor Coding: Actual

Drug content (%)

Design Points:

● Above Surface
 ○ Below Surface
 89 99.1

X1 = A
 X2 = B

Actual Factor
 C = 26.5

Fig no.14:3-D response surface plot for effect of concentration of olive oil, span80 and tween 60 on drug content

Table no.8 : Fit summary

Source	Sequential p-value	Lack of fit p-value	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R ²	
Liner	0.0141		0.4958	0.2336	

2FI	0.1921		0.6042	0.4318	
Quadratic	0.0002		0.9857	0.9065	Suggested
Cubic	0.0460		0.9999	0.9855	Aliased

Table no. 7: ANOVA for Quadratic model**Response 1: In-vitro drug release**

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	
Model	147.65	9	16.41	24.74	0.0013	Significant
A-olive oil	14.74	1	14.74	22.22	0.0053	
B-span 80	9.24	1	9.24	13.92	0.0135	
C-tween 60	61.75	1	61.75	93.11	0.0002	
AB	0.0036	1	0.0036	0.0054	0.9440	
AC	11.26	1	11.26	16.97	0.0092	
BC	9.10	1	9.10	13.71	0.0140	
A ²	0.3415	1	0.3415	0.5150	0.5051	
B ²	36.75	1	36.75	55.42	0.0007	
C ²	0.3322	1	0.3322	0.5009	0.5107	
Residual	3.32	5	0.6632			
Cor total	150.96	14				

Table no. 9: ANOVA for Quadratic model**Response 1: Drug content**

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	
Model	143.80	9	15.98	108.44	<0.0001	Significant
A-olive oil	3.36	1	3.36	22.83	0.0050	
B-span 80	28.22	1	28.22	191.56	<0.0001	
C-tween 60	55.70	1	55.70	378.01	<0.0001	
AB	5.95	1	5.95	40.39	0.0014	
AC	10.81	1	10.81	73.38	0.0004	
BC	7.80	1	7.80	52.95	0.0008	
A ²	12.70	1	12.70	86.19	0.0002	
B ²	22.80	1	22.80	154.75	0.0001	
C ²	1.56	1	1.56	10.56	0.0227	
Residual	0.7376	5	0.1473			
Cor total	144.54	14				

The desirability function approach is one of the most widely used methods for optimization. Overall, the desirability function measures how well the combined goals for all responses are satisfied. The numerical optimization tool provided 6 sets of optimal solutions, among which 11 ml of olive oil, 52 ml of Span 80, and 10 ml of Tween 60 were selected by the software as the optimized concentrations with a desirability of 1.0.

The area of the optimized formulation was also validated using an overlay plot, as shown in Fig. No. 14, where the yellow region represents the area satisfying the imposed criteria. To confirm the validity of the obtained optimal formulation, experiments were carried out in triplicate at the optimal combinations of the factors (X1=11, X2=52, X3=10).

Table no. 10: Desirability table showing solutions suggested and its desirability

Number	Olive oil	Span 80	Tween 60	Invitro drug release	StdErr(Invitro drug release)	Drug content	StdErr(Drug content)	Desirability	
1	11.000	52.000	10.000	98.958	0.727	99.419	0.343	1.000	Selected
2	11.368	52.000	10.000	98.868	0.707	99.600	0.333	1.000	
3	11.233	52.000	10.000	98.901	0.714	99.535	0.337	1.000	
4	11.178	52.000	10.000	98.915	0.717	99.508	0.338	1.000	
5	11.307	52.000	10.000	98.883	0.710	99.570	0.335	1.000	
6	11.439	52.000	10.000	98.850	0.704	99.633	0.332	1.000	

Factor Coding: Actual

Overlay Plot

Invitro drug release

Drug content

● Design Points

X1 = A

X2 = B

Actual Factor

C = 10

Fig no.15: Overlay plot of optimized formulation of SDEDDS of Simvastatin**CONCLUSION:**

This study successfully demonstrated that the Self Double Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SDEDDS) formulation could significantly enhance the solubility and dissolution rate of simvastatin. The selection of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant was optimized to achieve maximum efficacy, as evidenced by the favorable drug release profile. The optimized formulation exhibited desirable properties such as high drug content, short emulsification time, and stability, as indicated by the high cloud point and suitable zeta potential. The SDEDDS formulation was able to hold a good amount of the drug, mixed quickly and easily, and remained stable. These results indicate that this method could make simvastatin more effective by improving how much of the drug gets absorbed into the body, making it a promising option for better drug delivery.

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